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Detecting Fake News in Hindi Using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Techniques

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Abstract

Fake news has become a significant challenge in today's digital ecosystem, influencing public opinion and causing societal harm. The rapid spread of misinformation and fake news poses a significant challenge to Indian society, especially given the diversity of languages and the popularity of the social media platforms. More people than ever are sharing information thanks to social media, affordable phones, and data plans, but much of it is not accurate. In this work, Hindi news articles from various news sources are collected. This work explores Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) approaches for detecting fake news in Hindi news articles. Implemented traditional ML Models – Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest, and Naïve Bayes using TF-IDF features and an LSTM Deep Learning model using tokenized sequences. The experiments show that LSTM outperforms ML models, achieving 83% accuracy and AUC of 0.89, compared to 77-79% for ML models. This report discusses methodology, results, and future improvements.

1. Introduction

In the past, people received information from a variety of trusted sources that adhered to established standards and guidelines. These traditional channels were expected to maintain a certain level of integrity, ensuring that the information they provided was reliable and followed ethical norms. However, with the advent and widespread availability of the internet, new methods for sharing and distributing information have emerged. These contemporary techniques often lack the formal guidelines, ethical considerations, or benchmarks that once governed the flow of information. As a result, information can now be circulated with minimal oversight, leading to challenges in maintaining accuracy and reliability.

Today, most people get their news from online sources and social media, making it challenging to verify stories. The shift from trusted news outlets to digital platforms means information spreads fast but is harder to confirm. The proliferation of fake news has become a global concern, impacting elections, public health and social stability (Conroy et al., 2015; Raza & Ding, 2022; World Economic Forum, 2025; CU Boulder Today, 2025)

Detecting fake news in regional languages like Hindi is particularly challenging due to linguistic diversity and limited resources. In India as per early 2025 survey, there are almost 1.23 billion mobile connections and out of which approximately 86% of them are having smartphone with internet connection (Telecom Regulatory Authority of India, 2025; Techjury, 2024). So, this number plays a significant role in spreading any news and promoting any agenda which is not real and can be dangerous for society. The lack of oversight in information sharing has enabled fake news to spread rapidly for political and commercial purposes (Doddapaneni et al., 2023; Kumar & Josan, 2010).

Using machine learning for automated fake news detection can potentially help limit misinformation and contribute to improved media literacy. This work aims to compare ML and DL models for fake news detection in Hindi, focusing on accuracy, interpretability, and scalability. The models developed in this study are designed to analyze articles and determine their authenticity. Each tested model accepts a given article as input and processes it to classify the article as either fake or real. This automated classification enables efficient and scalable detection of fake news within Hindi news articles, providing a practical approach for handling large volumes of content spread across digital platforms (Li et al., 2022; Villela et al., 2023).

2. Research Background

2.1 Significance of Fake News Detection

The internet and social media have made sharing information easier and faster than ever, but they've also paved the way for fake news to spread rapidly. Because anyone can post content and there's little oversight, both reliable and misleading information circulate freely. This accessibility turns social media into a breeding ground for false stories, creating serious challenges for society. Fake news has become a global phenomenon, influencing elections, financial markets, public health decisions, and social stability (World Economic Forum, 2025; CU Boulder Today, 2025).

The rapid spread of misinformation through digital platforms poses severe challenge for an individual knowledge base root and also for governments to take right stands and decision. The flood of news from countless sources and social media often traps people in narrow viewpoints. Seeing the same kinds of stories repeatedly can restrict how we think and what we believe—even when the information is misleading. This issue is made worse today, as false or harmful stories spread almost instantly. The consequences go beyond personal opinions, threatening the reputation of companies and the stability of financial markets. Unchecked fake news damages informed decisions and can have broad effects across society and the economy.

There was a recent example of impact of Fake news in personal individual's life – In the first week of November 2025 saw the wave of reports from different social media accounts and even some online news channels that claimed Famous actor Dharmendra had died. The news travelled like wildfire, causing confusion, grief and emotional suffering. But then, the family came to scene with loudest, clearest, and most conclusive denial of them all (CyberPeace, 2025; Wikipedia, n.d.).

This example illustrates how an entire society's attention can be diverted, and families can be adversely affected, by news that is manipulated or fabricated rather than accurate and reliable. Although, there are several fact checking news agencies, but still detecting fake news in regional language like Hindi is particularly critical because of large user base and lack of robust language-specific tools (Alt News Hindi, n.d.; Press Trust of India, n.d.).

2.2 Approaches in Fake News Detection

Fake news detection primarily relied on traditional machine learning models such as Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Naïve Bayes. These models use statistical features like term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) to classify text. While effective for basic text classification tasks, these models often fail to capture semantic relationship and word order, which are essential for understanding nuanced language patterns (Li et al., 2022; Sammut & Webb, 2011).

Deep Learning models, particularly Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, have revolutionized text classification by capturing sequential dependencies and contextual meaning. Unlike traditional ML models, LSTM can process variable-length sequences and retain long-term dependencies, making it suitable for complex language tasks such as fake news detection. Recent studies have shown that LSTM and transformer-based models outperform traditional approaches in accuracy and generalization (Hong & Wang, 2023; Liu, 2024; Raza et al., 2025).

2.3 Challenges in Hindi Language Processing

Hindi, being morphologically rich and syntactically complex, present unique challenge for NLP tasks. Limited availability of annotated datasets, diverse dialects, and lack of pre-trained embeddings for Hindi contribute to the complexity of fake news detection in this language. Addressing these challenges requires advanced feature engineering and robust model

architectures (Kumar & Josan, 2010; Rajwal, 2023; Rani & Lobiyal, 2022; Doddapaneni et al., 2023).

3. Proposed Solution

The identification of fake news presents a sophisticated challenge that requires the analysis of textual data. Consequently, natural language processing (NLP) techniques play a critical role in both pre-processing and feature engineering stages. These steps help prepare the data so that it can be effectively analyzed and classified.

Multiple machine learning and deep learning approaches are utilized to classify news articles as fake or true. The classification process typically begins with collecting a suitable dataset, which forms the foundation for subsequent analysis and modeling.

3.1 Dataset

A major obstacle in developing effective fake news detection systems is the limited availability of high-quality datasets, especially for languages other than English. While numerous datasets exist for the English language, resources for Hindi are comparatively scarce. To address this gap in the current project, the ‘‘Hindi Fake News Detection Dataset’’ from Kaggle has been utilized. This dataset comprises news articles sourced from a variety of reputable Hindi news channel websites, including BBC-Hindi and NDTV, as well as verified fact-checking websites. The diversity and reliability of these sources ensure that the dataset is suitable for building robust models for fake news detection in Hindi (Kaggle, n.d.).

- **Size:** 17,124 articles
- **Labels:** 0 = True news, 1 = Fake news
- **Columns:** #, text, label, wcount
- True News count: 9, 944
- Fake news count: 7,180

Figure 1

Sample Dataset

Unnamed: 0		text	label	wcount
0	0	'मोदी के शासन के दौरान गंगा' गंगा नदी नरेन्द...	1	19
1	1	यह खबर आने से पहले छवि क्रेडिट जस्टिन सुलिवान/...	1	374
2	2	गुलाब गेंद वाल डे-नाइट टेस्ट मैच कप्ता विराट क...	0	20
3	3	उत्तर कोरिया रॉकेट प्रक्षेपण योजनाएं 71 0 15 0...	1	345
4	4	राष्ट्रपति डोनाल्ड ट्रम्प और प्रथम महिला मेलान...	0	180

3.2 Preprocessing

As raw text serves as training data for machine learning models, it must be transformed into numerical representations prior to training because these algorithms cannot interpret textual data directly. Preprocessing involves preparing and refining data to improve the effectiveness of model performance. This step is crucial for ensuring that the input is suitable for analysis and modeling.

Preprocessing encompasses a variety of techniques and procedures that prepare the data for effective learning. Several important steps in the preprocessing pipeline are discussed in the following sections, each addressing specific aspects of data cleaning and transformation needed for robust fake news detection.

3.2.1 Text Cleaning

Text cleaning involves systematically addressing various imperfections and inconsistencies present in the dataset. This process includes removing null entries, eliminating unnecessary or irrelevant information, correcting incorrectly formatted data, and filtering out noise that could hinder analysis. By performing these cleaning steps, the dataset becomes more uniform and reliable, which directly contributes to increased overall productivity and improved model performance during subsequent analysis and machine learning tasks.

Figure 2

Cleaned dataset overview

Index: 17123 entries, 0 to 17123			
Data columns (total 4 columns):			
#	Column	Non-Null Count	Dtype
0	Unnamed: 0	17123 non-null	int64
1	text	17123 non-null	object
2	label	17123 non-null	int64
3	wcount	17123 non-null	int64

dtypes: int64(3), object(1)

3.2.2 Stop-word removal

Stop words are common words in a language (like “the”, “is”, “and” in English; “के”, “है”, “और” in Hindi) that carry little unique meaning and appear very frequently. These words do not affect the overall outcome and may be omitted prior to the training process.

Why remove stop words?

- **Reduce Noise:** Stop-words don’t help distinguish between fake and real news (or most other text classification tasks).
- **Improve Model Performance:** Removing them makes model focus on more meaningful words.
- **Reduce Dimensionality:** Fewer words mean smaller feature space, which helps algorithms run faster and generalize better.

For this project, Hindi stop-words are collected from python library “hindi-stopwords” (PyPI, n.d.; Rajwal, 2023)

Figure 3

Hindi Stop-words

Total Hindi stopwords: 266
['अंदर', 'अत', 'अदि', 'अपना', 'अपनि', 'अपने', 'अभी', 'अथवा', 'अगर', 'अति', 'अथ', 'अब', 'आदि', 'आप', 'इत्यादि', 'इन', 'इनका', 'इन्हीं', 'इन्हें', 'इस', 'इसका', 'इसकि', 'इसके', 'इसमें', 'इसी', 'इसे', 'उन्हें', 'उनका', 'उनकि', 'उनके', 'उनको', 'उपर', 'उहीं', 'उसी', 'उसे', 'एक', 'एवं', 'ऐसे', 'और', 'कई', 'कर', 'करता', 'करते', 'करना', 'करने', 'करें', 'कहते', 'कहा', 'का', 'काफी', 'कि', 'कितु', 'की', 'कुछ', 'कुल', 'कृपया', 'के', 'को', 'कौन', 'कौनसा', 'गया', 'घर', 'जब', 'जहाँ', 'जैसे', 'जैसा', 'जिन', 'जिन्हें', 'जिन्हीं', 'जिस', 'जिसे', 'जुका', 'तक', 'तब', 'तरह', 'तिन', 'तिन्हें', 'तिन्हीं', 'तिस', 'तिसे', 'तो', 'था', 'थी', 'थे', 'दबारा', 'दिया', 'दूसरा', 'दो', 'द्वारा', 'न', 'नहीं', 'ना', 'निचे', 'नीचे', 'ने', 'पर', 'पहले', 'पूरा', 'फिर', 'बनी', 'बना', 'बने', 'बात', 'बाद', 'बाला', 'बिलकुल', 'भी', 'भीतर', 'मार', 'मानो', 'मे', 'में', 'यदि', 'यह', 'यहाँ', 'यही', 'या', 'यानी', 'यूँ', 'ये', 'रखें', 'रहा', 'रहे', 'रखी', 'रखें', 'लिए', 'लिये', 'लेकिन', 'ब', 'बौरह', 'बर्ग', 'वह', 'वहाँ', 'वाले', 'वास्तव', 'वास्तव में', 'वे', 'वो', 'शायद', 'संग', 'संगी', 'सबसे', 'सामने', 'सही', 'साख्य', 'सी', 'साथ', 'साभार', 'से', 'सो', 'ही', 'हुआ', 'हुई', 'हुए', 'है', 'हैं', 'हो', 'होता', 'होती', 'होते', 'होना', 'होने', 'अबतक', 'अलग', 'अक्सर', 'अतिरिक्त', 'अपेक्षाकृत', 'अरे', 'असल में', 'असल', 'आदि', 'आपका', 'आपके', 'इसलिए', 'इसलिये', 'इसलिये', 'उसीलिए', 'कुछ भी', 'कितना', 'किस', 'किसी', 'किसे', 'क्यों', 'क्योंकि', 'खासकर', 'गौरतलब', 'चाहे', 'जिनके', 'जिनसे', 'जितना', 'जैसा कि', 'जैसे कि', 'जहाँ तक', 'तदनुसार', 'तब तक', 'तबसे', 'तुम', 'तुम्हारा', 'तुम्हारी', 'तुम्हारे', 'थोड़ा', 'थोड़ी', 'थोड़े', 'देर', 'ध्यान से', 'नए', 'नयी', 'नया', 'पल', 'पहुँच', 'प्रति', 'बजाय', 'बिलकुल नहीं', 'बेहद', 'भले ही', 'मात्र', 'मत', 'मानिए', 'मुझे', 'मुझसे', 'मुझको', 'मेरा', 'मेरे', 'मेरी', 'रखना', 'लाभ', 'लागत', 'लागती', 'लागते', 'लगा', 'लागाया', 'लगाने', 'वाले', 'वाला', 'वाली', 'विषय में', 'सकता', 'सकती', 'सकते', 'सब', 'सभी', 'सिर्फ', 'सिर्फ', 'सुनिए', 'उसके बाद', 'उसमें', 'उससे', 'उसको', 'उसे', 'उसका', 'उतना', 'एसा', 'ऐसा', 'ऐसी', 'ऐसे', 'इसमें से', 'करेगा', 'करोगे', 'करँगा', 'करेंगे', 'करेंगे', 'करेंगे', 'किए', 'किया', 'कीजिए', 'कीजिये']

3.2.3 Stemming

Stemming is a text normalization technique used to reduce words to their root or base form. This process helps in minimizing variations of the same word. For this project, the Snowball Stemmer for Hindi is applied to remove suffixes and converts words into their stemmed form. For example, words like “खबरें” and “खबरों” were normalized to “खबर” (PyPI, n.d.; Pandey & Siddiqui, 2011).

Figure 4
Stemmed texts

	clean_text	stemmed_text
0	मोदी शासन दौरान गंगा गंगा नदी नरेन्द्र मोदी शा...	मोद शासन दौरान गंग गंग नद नरेन्द्र मोद शाशन का...
1	खबर आने छवि क्रेडिट जस्टिन सुलिवानगेटी द रियल ...	खबर आन छव क्रेडिट जस्टिन सुलिवानगेट द रियल एजे...
2	गुलाब गेंद वाल डेनाइट टेस्ट मैच कप्ता विराट को...	गुलाब गेंद वाल डेनाइट टेस्ट मैच कप्त विराट कोह...
3	उत्तर कोरिया रॉकेट प्रक्षेपण योजनाएं जापान दक्...	उत्तर कोरिय रॉकेट प्रक्षेपण योज जापान दक्षिण क...
4	राष्ट्रपति डोनाल्ड ट्रम्प प्रथम महिला मेलानिया...	राष्ट्रपत डोनाल्ड ट्रम्प प्रथम महिल मेलानिय द्...

3.2.4 Tokenization

After cleaning and stemming, tokenization was applied to split text into individual tokens (words). This step ensures that subsequent processes like stop-word removal and stemming can be performed effectively.

3.3 Data Splitting

After preprocessing, the dataset was divided into training and testing subsets using an 80:20 ratio to ensure unbiased evaluation of model performance. The training set was used for model training, while the test set was reserved for validation.

Figure 5
Dataset divisions

	Set	Samples count
0	Total datasets samples	17124
1	Training dataset samples	13699
2	Testing dataset samples	3425

4. Methodology

4.1 Feature Engineering

Feature engineering is the process of transforming raw data into meaningful representations that improve the performance of machine learning models. In text classification tasks, this involves converting unstructured text into numerical features that algorithms can interpret. For this project, two primary techniques were applied: TF-IDF, which captured the importance of words based on their frequency, and Tokenization, which converts text into sequence suitable for deep learning models like LSTM.

Figure 6
Feature Engineering Architecture (GeeksforGeeks, 2025; Sammut & Webb, 2011)

4.1.1 Term frequency – Inverse document frequency (TF-IDF)

Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) is a widely used feature extraction technique for text classification. It assigns weights to words based on their frequency in a document and their rarity across entire corpus. This helps highlight words that are important for distinguishing between classes. In this project TF – IDF was applied to convert text into numerical vectors for machine learning models. TF-IDF consists of two primary components (Sammut & Webb, 2011; GeeksforGeeks, 2025):

1. Term Frequency (TF): Indicates the frequency with which a word occurs within a document. A higher term frequency typically signifies more relevance.

$$TF(t, d) = \frac{\text{Number of times term } t \text{ appears in document } d}{\text{Total numbers of words in document } d(d)} \quad \text{eq. (1)}$$

2. Inverse Document Frequency (IDF): This metric diminishes the significance of words frequently appearing across numerous documents, while it enhances the importance of terms that are less commonly found.

$$IDF(t, D) = \log \left(\frac{\text{Total number } (N) \text{ of documents in corpus } D}{\text{Number of documents } (D) \text{ containing term } t} \right) \quad \text{eq. (2)}$$

This balance enables TF-IDF to identify terms that are both prevalent within individual documents and distinctive across an entire collection. The TF-IDF score is calculated by multiplying term frequency by inverse document frequency, as demonstrated in the equation (3) below:

$$TF - IDF(t, d, D) = TF(t, d) \times \log \left(\frac{N}{DF(t)} \right) \quad \text{eq. (3)}$$

Here,

- 't' denotes a term
- 'd' represents a document

- 'D' refers to the corpus
- TF (t, d) signifies the term frequency of term 't' within document 'd'.
- 'N' indicates the total number of documents.
- DF(t) refers to the number of documents containing the term 't'.

Figure 7

Top 20 words in the dataset ranked by average TF-IDF score

4.1.2 Tokenization

Tokenization is the process of splitting text into smaller units called tokens (usually words) and converting them into numerical representations. For deep learning model like LSTM, tokenization is essential because these models require integer sequence as input. In this project Tokenization was performed using Keras Tokenizer to convert words into integer sequences. Each word was assigned a unique index based on its frequency in the training corpus (Medium, n.d.)

Figure 8

Example of tokenization showing conversion of Hindi text into integer sequences

Tokenization Example:

Original: ओबामा ने झूठ बोला-विकीलीक्स राष्ट्रपति ओबामा को क्लिंटन के ईमेल से घबराहट

Tokenized Sequence: [402, 667, 16, 26, 74, 4138]

Original: यह खबर फर्जी है

Tokenized Sequence: [95, 376]

4.2 Algorithms

This dataset has been evaluated using a range of machine learning and deep learning algorithms. The methods applied include Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest, Naïve Bayes, and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), which will be discussed in the subsequent sections.

4.2.1 Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a supervised machine learning algorithm designed for classification tasks. It is primarily employed for binary classification, where the outcome belongs to one of two categories, such as Yes/No, True/False, or 0/1.

Logistic regression utilizes the sigmoid function to transform input values into probabilities ranging between 0 and 1.

$$\sigma(z) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}, \text{ where } z = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \dots + \beta_n x_n \quad \text{eq. (4)}$$

The screenshot below presents both the predicted and actual results obtained from training with logistic regression.

Figure 9

Example of generated result from the model's prediction using logistic regression

Sr. No.	Statements	Prediction	Actual
1	त कुत्त पैख बराबर जिसक जीत साफ कर बदब आएगी।	Not Fake	Not Fake
2	मंगलवार नयंबर आत हैथोडाथोड़ करके। दुनिय भर पुरातत्वविद यरूशलेम हाल उस चीज़ खोज उत्साहित पैगंबर डैनियल आखिर भविष्यवाण म ज है। प्रकार पढ़ ज डैनियल अंतिम भविष्यवाण देख अंतिम दिन लोग चमक बक्स देख भ्रमित जायेंगे। भीड़भाड़ जगह बैठ गोल घूर खुद बात व्यस्त सप्ताहांत वेश्य हंसेंगे। स्वभाव गुप्तांग बार भ्रमित होंग एकदूसर आकर्षण मासूमियत संदेह करेगे। पुरुष पुरुष बच्च पैद कोशिश महिल शरीर शरीर पैद कोशिश करेगी। ज पढ़ बत ज उस बिन प्रश्न विश्वास ल स्वप्न वास्तविक बीच अंतर असमर्थ जायेंगे। होंग नौद चल रह ज कह आत कह ज मन होंगे। मन उस दुष्ट पूज आज़ापालन ज मन अवतार होंग शक्त प्रसिद्ध भगवान लूसिफ़ेर। कह दीज वैसे होंग बात घटित देख जान ल अन्त निकट है। आंट मैटर बन	Not Fake	Fake
3	भ अगल बार पंचर दुकान पंचर बनव ज पुर टायर लेकर आन देश जल ज	Not Fake	Not Fake
4	ज्यादातर कंपनी मिल लोन रिस्ट्रक्चरिंग फायद जान	Not Fake	Not Fake

Advantage of using Logistic regression is - It is simple, interpretable, and effective for text classification when combined with TF-IDF feature.

Limitations of using Logistic regression is – it cannot capture word order or complex semantic relationship.

4.2.2 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is supervised learning algorithm that is used for classification, regression and find the optimal hyperplane to separate classes.

The screenshot below displays the predicted outcomes alongside the actual results obtained from training with an SVM model:

Figure 10

Example of generated result from the model's prediction using SVM

Sr. No.	Statements	Prediction	Actual
1	ब्योर्क डर पीछ हट संस्करण पिटिंग न्यूवोस मिनिस्टेरियोस एल कॉर्ट इंगलिस एलेवेटर चल ज काम ज्यलंत संस्करण मन है। वेबसाइट विश्लेषण कुकीज़ उपयोग कर साइट उपयोग कैसे ज है। कुकीज़ आपक पहचान सक ब्राउज़र जार रख कुकीज़ नीत स्वीकार है। मैं सहमत हूं। जानकारी।	Fake	Fake
2	लॉन्च रुपय प्रीपेड प्लान	Not Fake	Not Fake
3	फूड स्टॉल चल वाल क प्रसाद डोनेशन पैस ल लग हेराफेर आरोप यूट्यूबर किय धोखाधड़ इनकार	Not Fake	Not Fake
4	ट्रैपेनस्टीन मैं प्रेस स्वतंत्र बहुत बड़ विश्वास रख हूं। ज्यादा मजबूत को विश्वास भयानक भयानक गलत गलत लोग चोट पहुंच उद्देश्य ज है। द डोनाल्ड जैस सार्वजनिक हस्त प्रेस मुकदम जानबूझ लोग चोट पहुंच झूठ छाप है। अमेरिक कानून तहत मानक वास्तविक द्वेष आवश्यक प्रकार परिभाषित जान कथन झूठ कथन सत्य असत्य लापरवाह उपेक्ष कार्य करना। ट्रम्प लोकलभावन व्यक्त बौद्धिक रूप आलस व्यक्त ज ज मैं सुन हूं अलाव शोध सीध जानता।	Fake	Fake

Advantage of using SVM is – It is effective in high dimensional spaces and Limitation of using SVM is – It is computationally expensive for large datasets and lacks sequential context understanding.

4.2.3 Naive Bayes

The Naive Bayes algorithm is a classification technique grounded in Bayes' theorem. This method operates under the assumption that features are mutually independent, hence the term "naive." It determines the likelihood that a given sample belongs to a specific class by calculating probabilities based on its individual features. The Naive Bayes formula is concisely represented by the following equation:

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B)*P(B|A)}{P(B)} \quad eq. (5)$$

Where:

P(A): The probability that event A occurs

P(B): The probability that event B occurs

P(B|A): The probability that event B occurs given that event A has already occurred

P(A|B): The probability that event A occurs given that event B has already occurred

By applying the TF-IDF method, the significance of each word in the headline is quantified under the assumption that the news is fake. These values are converted into probabilities, which are then applied using Bayes' theorem to assess the likelihood that a given headline is fake, assuming the headline is real.

The screenshot below presents the predicted and actual results obtained from training with the Naive Bayes algorithm:

Figure 11

Example of generated result from the model's prediction using Naive Bayes

Sr. No.	Statements	Prediction	Actual
1	अमांड फ़ोएलिच पेड्ड जैस गगनचूब इमारत एकड फसल उग सक्षम पूर नवीकरणीय संसाधन संचालित होगी। विश्व जनसंख्य पहुँच अनुमान	Not Fake	Fake
2	हिन सोन लडक परिजन परेशान होकर पहुँच पुलिस पास हिन हिंद रीत रिवाज शाद शाद सोन नाम रख बर्र गुजैन नितेश लव मैरिज परिजन देत जान मार धमक बर्र गुजैन मर्दनपुर गांव मामला।	Not Fake	Not Fake
3	ैयाजीकहिन हिंदुस्तान प्रहार चीन साजिश तारतार	Not Fake	Not Fake
4	आ बार बिल्कुल स्पष्ट रह हिडन फैसेस नाम को फिल्म है। गोल्डन ग्लोब्स देख अस्तित्वहीन फिल्म बार उल्लेख अन्यथ सोच आपक माफ जाएगा। पहल बार निश्चित रूप गल दूसर बार इत स्पष्ट एनबीएस जेन बुश हेगर गोल्डन ग्लोब्स रिपोर्टिंग पहल मोड लेत संभवतः फैरेल विलियम्स हिडन फिगर्स सर्वश्रेष्ठ मूल स्कोर नामांकन बार पूछ चाह थ ज तीन अश्वेत महिल बार फिल्म ज अमेरिक अंतरिक्ष कार्यक्रम महत्वपूर्ण भूमिक निभाएंगी। निश्चित रूप इराद फैसेस बार पूछ ज वियोल डेविस डेन्जेल् वाशिंगटन अभिनीत समान रूप प्रसिद्ध फिल्म थी। श्र विलियम्स को भागीदार थी। श्र विलियम्स प्रतिक्रिय जिसम ज कह चाह रोक पूर कोशिश दिख संयम प्रभावशाल थी। आश्चर्य द्विटर तत्काल प्रतिक्रिय कम संयमित थी। जेन बुश आज रात ोल्डनग्लोब्स काल फिल्म विलय रह यूजर पूछ दूसर फैरेल चेहर सैकड़ वर्ष सफेद संकल्प मौजूद है। अन्य लोग फिल्म शीर्षक आविष्कार मज आया। लग चीज खत्म ग कारण माइकल कीटन मोशन पिक्चर सर्वश्रेष्ठ सहायक अभिनेत्र नामांकित व्यक्त सूच बन समय हिडन फैसेस उल्लेख किया। चूक कैमर अभिनेत्र केंद्रित स्पष्ट मिस्टर कीटन आंख मार सिर हिल था।	Not Fake	Not Fake

One key advantage of Naive Bayes is its effectiveness with categorical inputs. Additionally, its computational efficiency enables rapid predictions, contributing to significant time savings.

One limitation of the Naïve Bayes algorithm is its assumption that all input variables are mutually independent, an occurrence that is uncommon in practical scenarios. For instance, if the title "Narendra Modi" appears, the algorithm treats "Narendra" and "Modi" as separate, independent inputs, which does not accurately reflect their relationship. This assumption restricts the applicability of the algorithm in many real-world contexts.

4.2.4 Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) is an advanced form of the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). LSTM networks are designed to capture long-term dependencies within sequential data, making them well-suited for applications such as language translation, speech recognition, and time series forecasting.

LSTM networks are employed within the field of deep learning. Unlike traditional feedforward neural networks, LSTM architectures incorporate feedback connections. They feature a unique memory unit capable of retaining information over extended time intervals.

LSTM architectures incorporate a memory cell that is regulated by three distinct gates:

- Input gate: Determines which information is incorporated into the memory cell.
- Forget gate: Specifies which information is discarded from the memory cell.
- Output gate: Governs the information that is transmitted from the memory cell.

Figure 12*LSTM Model*

The screenshot below presents the predicted versus actual results obtained from training with an LSTM model:

Figure 13*Example of generated result from the model's prediction using LSTM*

Sr. No.	Statements	Prediction	Actual
1	कोरोन केसेस बहुत तेज बढ़ लग हैं। हम संक्रमण बच हम तीन चीज जन आंदोलन बन होग मास्क पहन सोशल डिस्टेंसिंग पालन साबुन हाथ धोना।	Not Fake	Not Fake
2	पूर करोन काल टीथ ज्यादा चर्चित नेत मोद ज जबक जलील मामल राहुल गांध नंबर वन	Not Fake	Not Fake
3	इलाहाबाद हाईकोर्ट गोरखपुर डॉक्टर कफील खान ऊपर हट आदेश तुरंत रिह निर्देश	Not Fake	Not Fake
4	एएफप सुरक्ष अधिकार चिकित्सक रविवार बगदाद मुख्य सञ्ज बाजार प्रवेश द्वार आत्मघ हमलावर कार उड़ जिसम कम कम लोग मार ग दर्जन घायल गए। आंतरिक मंत्रालय प्रवक्त साद मान जमील बाजार गेट सैनिक संदिग्ध वाहन देख आत्मघ कार बम गोलीबार आतंकवाद उसक कार उड़ दिया। पुलिस कर्नल अस्पताल अधिकार कम कम लोग मार ग घायल गए। मान घायल सैनिक शामिल जिस हमलावर गोल चलाई। जमील बगदाद मुख्य थीक सञ्ज बाजार सदर शहर स्थित ज राजधान उत्तरपूर्व विशाल ज्यादातर शिय इलाक बारबार निश बन है। हमल जिम्मेदार तत्काल को दाव हाल बम विस्फोट जिम्मेदार इस्लामिक स्टेट समूह सुन्न चरमपंथ ल है। आईएस दाव हालिय बड़ हमल जनवर सदर शहर आत्मघ हमलावर काम प्रतीक्ष दिहाइ मजदूर भीड़ बीच विस्फोटक भर वाहन उड़ जिसम लोग मार गए।	Not Fake	Not Fake

Advantages of the LSTM algorithm include its capacity to manage long-term dependencies and enhance predictive accuracy. It demonstrates superior performance over traditional RNNs by sustaining stable memory states throughout extended sequences. Nonetheless, issues such as overfitting and elevated computational requirements warrant careful attention during model development.

5. Results

To assess the performance of the models, some of the standard classification metrics were used. These metrics are derived from the confusion matrix, which consists of four components (Google Developers, n.d.; Ray, 2022):

- True Positive (TP): Fake news correctly classified as fake.

- False Positive (FP): True news incorrectly classified as fake.
- True Negative (TN): True news correctly classified as true.
- True Positive (TP): Fake news incorrectly classified as true.
- Accuracy: Accuracy measures the proportion of correctly classified instances among all instances.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad eq. (6)$$

- Precision: Precision indicates how many of predicted positive cases are actually positive.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad eq. (7)$$

- Recall: Recall shows how many actual positive cases were correctly identified.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad eq. (8)$$

- F1-Score: The F1-score is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, providing a balanced measure.

$$F1 - Score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision+recall} \quad eq. (9)$$

These metrics ensure a comprehensive evaluation of model performance. Accuracy alone may not be sufficient; therefore, Precision, Recall, and F1-score were considered to provide deeper insights into classification insights (Google Developers, n.d.; Ray, 2022).

5.1 Models Performance Summary

This section presents a comparative analysis of all trained models, including Logistic Regression, SVM (Support Vector Machine), Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, and LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory). Each model was evaluated using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score as defined above. Experiments were conducted with unigram and n-gram features, and hyperparameter tuning was applied where applicable (for Logistic Regression and SVM). Below table summarizes the performance of these models followed by a detailed discussion of key observation (Li et al., 2022; Raza & Ding, 2022).

Table 1

Summarizes the comparison of Models performance on Hindi News dataset.

Model	Features	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Logistic Regression	Unigram	74.8%	76%	60%	67%
Logistic Regression	N-gram	77.6%	81%	62%	70%
Logistic Regression (Tuned)	N-gram	77.5%	81%	62%	70%
SVM	Unigram	75.4%	75%	63%	69%
SVM	N-gram	76.5%	75%	66%	70%
SVM (Tuned)	N-gram	77.6%	81%	61%	70%
Naive Bayes	Unigram	74.9%	85%	49%	62%
Naive Bayes	N-gram	76.4%	83%	56%	67%

Random Forest	N-gram	78.7%	81%	65%	72%
LSTM	Tokenized	83.0%	82%	77%	79%

As shown in table 1 above, LSTM achieved the highest accuracy (83%) and balanced precision-recall, outperforming all machine learning models. Among ML models, Random Forest performed best (78.7%), followed by Logistic Regression and SVM with N-grams (~77%). Naive Bayes exhibited high precision but poor recall, indicating difficulty in detecting fake news consistently. The improvement from unigram to n-gram features across models suggests that incorporating word pair enhances contextual understanding. Hyperparameter tuning provided marginal gains, reinforcing that feature representation had a greater impact than parameter optimization.

Table 2

Top 3 best performing Models.

Model	Feature	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
LSTM	Tokenized	83.0%	82%	77%	79%
Random Forest	N-gram	78.7%	81%	65%	72%
Logistic Regression	N-gram	77.6%	81%	62%	70%

Table 2 clearly shows that LSTM performed better than all other models and it demonstrates the advantage of deep learning over traditional machine learning for text classification. LSTM achieved the highest accuracy and balanced precision-recall, making it the most effective for fake news detection. Random Forest performed better than other ML models, while logistic regression with N-grams showed competitive results, highlighting the importance of feature representation.

5.2 Discussion of Results

- **Best Performing Model:** LSTM achieved the highest accuracy (83%) and balanced precision-recall, outperforming all ML models.
- **Effect of N-grams:** Both Logistic regression and SVM improved slightly when using n-grams compared to unigrams, indicating that capturing word pairs adds contextual value.
- **Hyperparameter Tuning:** Minimal improvement was observed after tuning Logistic Regression and SVM, suggesting that feature representation had a greater impact than parameter optimization.
- **Naive Bayes:** While fast and simple, Naive Bayes struggled with recall for fake news, likely due to its independence assumption.
- **Random forest:** Performed better than other ML models but still fell short of LSTM, highlighting the advantage of sequential models for text data.

5.3 Visualization of Results

To provide a clearer understanding of model performance, several visualizations are generated. Below are some the performance visualizations:

5.3.1 Confusion Matrix

It illustrates the distribution of true positives, false positives, true negatives and false negatives. It shows the classification performance in terms of correct and incorrect predictions. Below are the confusion matrices for the ML models (Ray, 2022):

Figure 14

Confusion Metrics for ML models.

How to read the confusion matrix chart?

- **X-Axis (Predicted):** The number of labels predicted by the models
- **Y-axis (Actual):** The true class labels from test data
- **Diagonal Cells:** Correct Predictions

- **Off-Diagonal Cells:** Mistakes made by the model
- Top left in a chart shows correctly identified true news articles (Actual = 0 (True news), predicted = 0 (True News))
- Top right in a chart shows True news articles incorrectly classified as fake (Actual = 0 (True news), Predicted = 1 (Fake news))
- Bottom left in a chart shows Fake news articles incorrectly classified as true (Actual = 1 (Fake news), Predicted = 0 (True news))
- Bottom right in a chart shows correctly identified Fake news articles (Actual = 1 (Fake news), Predicted = 1 (Fake news))

5.3.2 ROC Curve

ROC stands for Receiver Operating Characteristic that illustrates the trade-off between False Positive rate and True Positive rate.

Figure 15

ROC Curve for LSTM Model.

In the Figure 13, The blue curve being above the diagonal line demonstrates that the model performs significantly better than random guessing. **AUC (Area Under Curve) of 0.89** shows that the model is much better than the random guessing. It can reliably distinguish between fake and true news most of the time.

5.3.3 Training History Plot

For LSTM model, the training history plots illustrates how the LSTM model learned over multiple epochs. Two key graphs are presented below to show the Training plot:

Figure 16

Training and Validation (Accuracy/Loss) for LSTM Model.

- **Accuracy Vs Epochs:** This graph shows the progression of training and validation accuracy across epochs. A steady increase in training accuracy indicates effective learning, while the plateau in validation accuracy after the first epoch suggest that model reached its optimal performance early.
- **Loss Vs Epochs:** This graph shows the reduction in training loss over time, confirming that model minimized error during training. However, the slight increase in validation loss after epoch one indicating mild overfitting.

These plots help assess the model's learning behavior and generalization capability. The divergence between training and validation curves highlights the importance of regularization strategies to prevent overfitting.

5.3.4 Bar Chart

Below Bar chart shows the accuracy and F1-Score of best performing models on the dataset of Hindi Fake news detection.

Figure 17

Accuracy and F1-score of "Top 3 Best Performing Models" for Hindi Fake news Detection.

This Bar Chart compares the accuracy and F1-Score of the three best performing model in this case of Hindi fake news detection study: LSTM, Random Forest and Logistic Regression

with n-grams. LSTM Achieved the highest accuracy (83%) and F1-Score (79%) followed by Random Forest and Logistic Regression.

6. Conclusion

This study focused on detecting Fake news in Hindi language using Machine learning and Deep Learning techniques. This study utilized a Kaggle dataset of Hindi News Articles that comprises of news articles from different fields. And used different Machine learning algorithms such as Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, SVM, Random Forest. Following an evaluation of various supervised learning algorithms, the deep learning model LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) was implemented to identify fake news in the Hindi language.

The first key contribution of this study is the comparative evaluation of different Machine Learning algorithms and Deep Learning Model for Fake news detection in Hindi Language. While ML models such as Logistic Regression and Random Forest achieved reasonable performance (accuracy ~78%), the LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) model significantly outperformed them with an accuracy of **83%** and balanced precision-recall scores.

The second key contribution of this study is the analysis of feature representation techniques. Incorporating n-grams improved ML models compared to unigram, highlighting the role of contextual features. However deep learning model using tokenized sequences provided superior results.

This study finds that certain fundamental machine learning and deep learning algorithms yield satisfactory results in addressing the critical issue of fake news dissemination. Despite these findings and detailed work, this research has limitations. The dataset size and diversity were one of the constrained that may affect generalization. Future work should explore the different type of datasets including images and using transformer-based architecture would improve the performance and scalability.

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